

worm

**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

D5.2. Standard operating procedure for donation and handover management

Date of delivery: **18/12/2025**

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**Funded by the
European Union**

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DOCUMENT TRACK INFORMATION

PROJECT INFORMATION	
Project acronym	WORM
Project title	Waste in humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimisation
Starting date	01/01/2024
Duration	24 months
Call identifier	HORIZON-CL6-2023-CIRC BIO-01
Grant Agreement No	101135392

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION	
Deliverable number	D5.2
Work Package number	WP5
Deliverable title	Standard operating procedure for donation and handover management
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Due date	31/12/2025
Submission date	18/12/2025
Type of deliverable	R
Dissemination level	PU

REVISION TABLE

VERSION	CONTRIBUTORS	DATE	DESCRIPTION
V0.1	Waqar Ahmed (IMC) Syed Yasir Ahmad (IMC)	13/10/2025	First draft
V0.2	Virva Tuomala (Hanken)	13/11/2025	Updated draft internally reviewed
V0.3	Waqar Ahmed (IMC) Syed Yasir Ahmad (IMC)	25/11/2025	Updated draft after contribution
V0.4	Virva Tuomala (Hanken)	16/12/2025	Updated draft after contribution
V0.5	Anaïs Loudières	16/12/2025	Updated draft after contribution
V0.6	Syed Yasir Ahmad (IMC)	1/12/2025	Updated draft after contribution
V1	Gyöngyi Kovács (Hanken)	18/12/2025	Final version for submission

LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	FULL NAME
EC	European Commission
EMT	Emergency medical team
EMTCC	Emergency medical team coordination cell
GIK	Gifts in kind
HO	Humanitarian Organization
HQ	Head quarter
IFRC	International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies
INN	International non-proprietary name
IPC	Infection prevention and control
MoH	Ministry of Health
MTL	Medical team lead
NGO	Non-governmental organization
PPE	Personal protective equipment
SOP	Standard operating procedure
TWG	Technical working group
WASH	Water, sanitation, and hygiene

WM	Waste management
WPs	Work Packages

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BACKGROUND ABOUT WORM

WORM aims to design guidelines and support actions for the circular economy in the humanitarian sector. It integrates bio-based technological solutions, leverages procurement to reduce waste, improves waste management practices, and prioritises the sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers. WORM focuses on two selected settings: field hospital deployments and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste-picking component. Following a collaborative, multi-actor approach, WORM brings together medical and humanitarian organisations, procurement service providers, logistics providers, waste management services, and academic partners.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the WORM Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101135392.

This document presents the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for the handover process of an EMT/field hospital. The handover process should begin as early as possible in the deployment planning stage, considering the deployment environment's contextual factors and the stakeholders who need to be involved. In a humanitarian operation, there are always risks and opportunities for both the HO and the deployment context.

Standardisation of processes is an established manner of running operations across the sector. The roles and responsibilities of the executing team must be clear to everyone involved, as well as to the receiving organization and/or stakeholders. There are multiple processes involved in the donation and handover, as outlined in this SOP. In the case of an EMT/field hospital, there are intricacies to consider, including sensitive items and materials, such as pharmaceuticals. This makes the SOP a valuable tool for HOs.

Using this SOP to execute an EMT deployment helps reduce waste and, therefore, improve environmental sustainability. The document outlines procedures for reuse, repair and refurbishment in EMT handover.

NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY

The purpose of this SOP is to provide a detailed, ethical, transparent, and systematic framework for the donation and handover of medical and non-medical items by Emergency Medical Teams (EMT) or field hospitals during, after, or between deployments. It ensures that all donated items are relevant, high-quality, aligned with recipient needs, and compliant with national and international standards.

This SOP operationalizes circularity principles and lifecycle-based asset management approaches developed under the WORM project, ensuring that the donation and handover processes:

- Contribute to waste reduction and environmental sustainability.
- Promote reuse, repair, refurbishment, and responsible reverse logistics.
- Prevent the unintended transfer of environmental burdens to local health systems.
- Strengthen accountability, transparency, and responsible integration of donated assets into local systems.
- Incorporate lessons, challenges, and best practices identified through WORM project activities, including multi-country workshops and technical consultations.

This SOP further ensures that all donation activities are need-driven, do not burden local systems, align with WHO EMT standards and national regulatory frameworks, comply with donor requirements, and are coordinated with Technical Working Groups, Ministries of Health, and relevant local stakeholders to support sustainable, safe, and context-appropriate asset transfer.

INTRODUCTION

An EMT is part of a humanitarian operation that is deployed through a needs-based assessment of the disaster situation on the ground. These decisions are made strategically by the organizations themselves, the receiving national governments, and other stakeholders associated with them. The decision to deploy a humanitarian team, including an EMT, is always a function of many factors, such as funding, resource availability, and time. However, the defining characteristic of a humanitarian operation is its temporary nature, meaning that at some point the deploying organisation must decide to close the operation (Muñoz Beaulieu et al., 2025). The closing decision may result from the disaster situation being declared over or from the HO's on-site funding ending. There are several ways a project can end: phasing out services gradually, abruptly withdraw, or handover to a local partner/stakeholder (Pal et al., 2019).

The IFRC (2022) highlights the importance of involving the local community in the handover process from the early phases of the operation, ideally before deployment. For example, maintaining the quality and sustainability of the hospital equipment and operation through establishing equipment repair and WM partnerships can only be achieved through local engagement and adequate handover processes. Without proper handover processes, there is a significant risk to the “do no harm” principle, as abrupt, poorly communicated exits leave communities unprepared for gaps in services caused by the operation.

In this deliverable, the focus is on the handover process of an EMT/field hospital operation to local stakeholders, with a focus on operationalising the continuity of sustainability and circularity principles in WM. This is achieved through SOPs, which provide step-by-step guidelines and instructions for handing over the circularity SOPs for an EMT deployment (D5.2) to local stakeholders. D5.3 presents WM guidelines to be used throughout the EMT operations.

Handing over medical operations, such as EMT/field hospitals, follows processes similar to those of other humanitarian operations, but the stakeholders differ by context (Sitali et al., 2022). An EMT handover involves stakeholders from the deploying HO to local NGOs, municipal governments, community members and the MoH. Figure 1 depicts the relief process of an EMT throughout the disaster management cycle, as well as the risks attached to improper medical WM and handover processes. However, there are also opportunities if WM processes are upheld and appropriate stakeholders are engaged.

Applying SOPs to a coordinated effort is essential if a standardised outcome is to be reached (Manghani, 2011). However, in handover situations, it is essential to engage with a wide range of stakeholders and conditions to best achieve the outcome (Zhao & Xia, 2014). The handover is usually initiated by the deploying HO in partnership with the MoH of the national government, but numerous other stakeholders play significant roles in the handover process. Municipal authorities, local partners, and local HOs can assist in overcoming the risks outlined by precarious infrastructure, societal vulnerabilities (enhanced by the disaster), and potentially secondary disaster caused by mismanaged medical waste. By standardising a default set of operating procedures across the sector, the complex interplay of decision making can be supported throughout the HOs that deploy EMTs (D5.1), as well as the local stakeholders that are handed over the operation, equipment, and material (D5.2).

Figure 1: The stakeholders of the handover.

This SOP operationalises the waste reduction by providing a continuing process to make medical WM in field hospitals sustainable. Through a handover process involving different governmental institutions, local authorities, and even informal actors such as waste pickers (D6.2), WORM, and this deliverable, the aim is to prevent the transfer of social and environmental burdens to local communities. Standardising operations is a crucial step in strengthening accountability and transparency of donated materials and equipment, as well as WM's best practices, for the appropriate stakeholders in the receiving community.

1. Background

1.1. Scope

This SOP applies to all EMT Types (1, 2, 3), Specialized care units, including fixed and mobile configurations. It covers both incoming and outgoing donations of medical commodities, including pharmaceuticals, vaccines, medical devices, diagnostics, personal protective equipment (PPE), and consumables. It also includes non-medical assets such as WASH infrastructure, tents, generators, logistics supplies and warehousing items, and digital tools. The SOP applies to donations made at the end of missions, during rotations, or upon special request from local actors. Transfers may be made to the national Ministries of Health (MoH), local public and private health facilities, humanitarian agencies, or other EMTs. The SOP addresses both donations from the EMT (outgoing donations) and those to the EMT (incoming donations), including gifts-in-kind (GIK). It integrates product lifecycle-based decisions, compatibility checks (technical, power, supply chain, maintenance), and circularity indicators.

1.2. Guiding principles

All donation and handover activities covered by this SOP must adhere to the following guiding principles to ensure that transfers are ethical, needs-driven, sustainable, and aligned with international standards.

- **Needs-Driven and Context-Appropriate:** Donations must be based on verified and documented needs identified through coordination with Ministries of Health (MoH), WHO EMTCC, and relevant clusters. Unsolicited or supply-driven donations are discouraged and may be declined.
- **Quality, Safety, and Regulatory Compliance:** All donated items must meet WHO prequalification norms, national regulatory requirements, and validated quality assurance protocols. Medical devices and pharmaceuticals must be functional, safe, and appropriate for the local context (infrastructure, language, maintenance capacity).
- **Ethical, Free of Charge, and Non-Commercial:** Donations must be provided at no cost to recipients. Resale, commercial redistribution, or use for profit is strictly prohibited. Donated items must support, not undermine, local health systems or existing supply chains.
- **Transparency, Documentation, and Traceability:** Each step of the donation lifecycle must be fully documented, verifiable, and signed by responsible personnel. Documentation must ensure full traceability, accountability, and audit readiness, in accordance with WHO and donor requirements.
- **Environmental Responsibility and Waste Prevention:** Items unsuitable for donation must be managed through safe, environmentally responsible disposal pathways, compliant with WHO and national protocols. Donations must not transfer environmental burdens to recipient systems.
- **Circularity and Lifecycle-Based Asset Management:** Donation and handover practices must integrate circular economy principles championed under the WORM Project, including:
 - Sustainable procurement and use of modular, repairable, reusable, and biodegradable items.
 - Maximizing reuse, repair, refurbishment, and repurposing before considering disposal.
 - Utilizing reverse logistics to retrieve, repurpose, or responsibly dispose of unsuitable items.
 - Ensuring donations do not create new waste streams or maintenance burdens that exceed local capacity.
- **Coordination and Collaboration:** All donation processes must be coordinated with MoH, WHO EMTCC, waste management authorities, Waste Management Committees or Technical Working

Groups (TWGs), and relevant cluster partners. Strong feedback loops must be established to adjust donation practices based on local capacity, lessons learned, and post-handover monitoring.

- **Do No Harm:** Donations must not introduce risks, create dependency, overwhelm local systems, or burden recipients with incompatible equipment or unusable consumables. Safety, sustainability, and long-term usability must guide every decision.

2. Roles and responsibilities

Effective donation and handover management relies on the coordinated efforts of a multidisciplinary team with clearly defined responsibilities. This section outlines the key personnel involved and emphasizes the importance of their collaboration to ensure that donations are ethical, appropriate, and sustainable. Special emphasis is placed on integrating technical expertise from biomedical engineers and waste management specialists to maximize the value of donated assets and minimize environmental and operational risks. These roles are central to achieving a smooth, complaint, and impact-driven donation process.

To ensure the sustainability, safety, and effectiveness of donation and handover processes, biomedical engineers and Waste Management Committees or Technical Working Groups (TWGs) play a critical role in the planning, execution, and post-transfer phases of EMT operations. The Logistics Coordinator and Medical Technician should collaborate with local artisans or biomedical engineers to assess the feasibility of repairing or refurbishing equipment prior to donation. Waste Management Committees or Technical Working Groups (TWGs) must be formed to oversee sustainable handover practices and ensure alignment with local infrastructure and capabilities.

Table 1: Summary of roles and responsibilities.

Role	Key responsibilities
Team Leader	Authorizes donation strategy, liaises with host authorities and EMTCC ensures overall compliance.
Medical Team Lead (MTL)	Evaluates clinical relevance and urgency of items for donation; ensures medical safety and appropriateness.
Pharmacist	Validates quality, shelf life, and legality of pharmaceuticals; manages controlled substances.
Biomedical Technician / Engineer/WASH Lead	Confirms functionality and safety of medical devices and diagnostics.
Logistics Coordinator	Manage inventory, packing, logistics, handover scheduling, and documentation.
Recipient Organization	Accepts the donation, signs documentation, ensures compliance and traceability.
Donor Focal Point	Ensures adherence to donor-specific requirements and reporting obligations (if applicable).
Waste management Committees/TWGs	Guide ethical and sustainable management of donated or surplus items by aligning practices with national and WHO standards. Advice on reuse, return, or disposal, coordinate with local stakeholders, ensure proper documentation and training, and promote knowledge sharing across deployments.

Team leader

The Team Leader holds overall accountability for the donation and handover process. They are responsible for authorizing the donation strategy in alignment with mission objectives, host country regulations, and EMTCC guidance. The Team Leader ensures that all donations are coordinated with national authorities, WHO, and relevant humanitarian clusters. They oversee the internal approval process, ensure that ethical and operational standards are upheld, and provide final sign-off on donation plans. The Team Leader also ensures that post-transfer monitoring and reporting obligations are fulfilled and that the process is transparent and auditable.

Medical Team Lead (MTL)

The MTL is responsible for evaluating the clinical relevance, safety, and appropriateness of items proposed for donation. This includes assessing whether the items are aligned with the recipient's treatment protocols, essential medicines list, and clinical capacity. MTL ensures that donated items do not pose a risk to patient safety and that they are usable within the recipient's healthcare setting. MTL also supports feasibility assessment and contributes to the development of training materials or guidance for the recipient on the use of donated items.

Medical Technician / Biomedical Engineer/WASH Lead

The Medical Technician or Biomedical Engineer/ WASH Lead is responsible for assessing the functionality, safety, and compatibility of medical devices and diagnostics intended for donation. They ensure that equipment is operational, includes user manuals, and is suitable for the recipient's infrastructure (e.g., power supply, maintenance capacity). They may also provide basic training to recipients on equipment use and maintenance and advice on the inclusion of spare parts and consumables. Their role is essential in preventing the donation of non-functional or inappropriate equipment.

Biomedical engineers are responsible for ensuring that all medical equipment and devices intended for donation are functional, safe, and compatible with the recipient's infrastructure. Their responsibilities include:

- Conducting technical assessments of equipment condition, usability, and repair potential.
- Verifying that donated devices meet safety standards and are appropriate for the local context (e.g., power supply, maintenance capacity).
- Supporting the classification of equipment for donation, refurbishment, or disposal.
- Providing technical documentation, user manuals, and maintenance guides with donated equipment.
- Training local staff in operation, basic maintenance, and troubleshooting of donated devices.
- Advising on the inclusion of spare parts and consumables to support continued use.
- Participating in post-handover support, including remote technical assistance.

Logistics Coordinator

The Logistics Coordinator manages the end-to-end logistics of the donation process. This includes inventory management, classification of items, packing, labeling, and scheduling of handover activities. They ensure that all documentation such as the Donation Certificate, Transfer of Ownership Form, and Packing List—is complete and accurate. The Logistics Coordinator also coordinates the physical transfer of items, ensures cold chain integrity where applicable, and supports post-transfer documentation and reporting. They liaise with transport providers, customs authorities, and local partners to facilitate smooth handovers.

Recipient organization

The Recipient Organization is responsible for formally accepting the donation and ensuring that it is used in accordance with agreed terms. This includes signing all relevant documentation, maintaining

traceability of donated items, and integrating them into their operations responsibly. The recipient must ensure that donated items are stored, used, and maintained appropriately, and that they do not enter commercial circulation. They may also be asked to provide feedback or participate in post-transfer monitoring to assess the impact and sustainability of the donation.

Donor Focal Point

If applicable, Donor Focal Point ensures that all donations comply with donor-specific requirements, including reporting, branding, and documentation standards. They review the donation plan to ensure alignment with donor agreements and may participate in the internal approval process. The Donor Focal Point also supports communication with the donor agency and ensures that all obligations—such as visibility, reporting, and audit readiness—are met.

Waste management committees/technical working groups (TGW)

These groups must be established to oversee the ethical, environmentally responsible, and context-appropriate management of surplus, damaged, or donated items. Their responsibilities include:

- Developing and reviewing SOPs for donation, handover, and disposal in line with national and WHO standards.
- Coordinating with EMT leadership, local authorities, and humanitarian partners to align donation practices with local needs and capacities.
- Monitoring the implementation of waste minimization strategies, including reuse, repair, and recycling.
- Advising on the selection of items for donation versus reverse logistics or disposal.
- Supporting the setup of segregation systems, compliant incineration, and environmentally sound disposal infrastructure.
- Facilitating knowledge exchange and innovation through national or regional TWGs, including sharing successful models and lessons learned.
- Ensuring that all handovers are accompanied by appropriate documentation, training, and post-transfer support mechanisms.

3. Donation and handover process

This section outlines and elaborates on the key steps involved in the donation lifecycle. The process is intended to maintain consistency, compliance, and coordination across all handovers.

3.1. Donation life-cycle

Figure 2: Donation process

Initiation of the donation process

The donation process begins when an EMT prepares for demobilization, conducts routine stock rotations, or receives a formal request for support from national authorities or local partners. During this stage, the team identifies surplus, redundant, unused, or repairable items that may be appropriate for donation. Before any items are confirmed for handover, the EMT must prioritize reverse logistics options such as recovery, refurbishment, or return-to-supplier schemes, ensuring that donation remains a last-resort option rather than the default. Circularity indicators, including remaining lifespan, repairability, and potential for reuse or recycling are assessed at this early stage. The initiation phase also includes preliminary consultations with EMT leadership, Ministry of Health focal points, and Waste Management Committees or Technical Working Groups to ensure alignment with national regulations, local needs, and sustainable end-of-life considerations. A preliminary list of items is then compiled and submitted for internal review.

Inventory & categorization

A comprehensive inventory is conducted to classify all potential donation items by type, condition, expiry status, and functional usability. This assessment covers pharmaceuticals, medical devices, PPE, WASH materials, digital tools, and logistics assets. Items are examined to determine whether they are new, lightly used, refurbished, repairable, or obsolete, and their suitability is further assessed through a circularity lens to determine whether they can be reused, repaired, recycled, refurbished, or require compliant disposal. Based on this analysis, items are sorted into three final groups: those eligible for donation, those appropriate for return via reverse logistics, and those that must be safely disposed of due to expiry, damage, contamination, or incompatibility. This step ensures that recipients are not burdened with unusable, unsafe, or environmentally harmful items.

Feasibility assessment

A detailed multidisciplinary review follows to confirm that the proposed donation is clinically appropriate, technically feasible, and environmentally responsible. The assessment verifies that pharmaceuticals align

with the national Essential Medicines List and that all donations meet regulatory, safety, and quality standards such as WHO prequalification. Equipment must be evaluated for compatibility with local infrastructure, including electrical systems, space requirements, power stability, and availability of supporting systems such as oxygen supply. The team also ensures that spare parts, consumables, and technical repair services are accessible in the recipient's context. The feasibility review assesses whether the recipient has the technical capacity to operate, maintain, and service the items. Environmental considerations, such as the recipient's ability to manage additional waste or end-of-life disposal, are also examined. Items that fail to meet the feasibility criteria are redirected to reverse logistics or compliant disposal. Items approved at this stage must be accompanied by user manuals, maintenance guides, training support, and, when possible, initial spare parts.

Recipient identification

Suitable recipients are identified based on coordination with the Ministry of Health, WHO EMTCC, and local humanitarian coordination structures, or based on direct requests from public health facilities, NGOs, and other EMTs. Selection is guided by the recipient's assessed needs, national health priorities, and capacity to responsibly manage and maintain the donated items. Only organizations with adequate operational, technical, and managerial capacity are considered to ensure that donations result in improved health service delivery rather than operational burdens or unintended costs.

Needs assessment & engagement

The EMT then undertakes structured engagement with the potential recipient to confirm their actual needs, readiness to receive the items, and capacity to use and maintain them effectively. This engagement verifies that the items are clinically relevant, appropriate, and aligned with the recipient's absorption capacity. The team assesses technical infrastructure such as power compatibility, storage conditions, cold chain capabilities, and available workspace. The recipient's capacity for maintenance, including technical workforce, access to spare parts, and routine servicing, is reviewed, along with their compliance with waste management and environmental safety requirements. Training needs are identified across clinical, maintenance, IPC, and safety domains. Joint assessments typically use standardized checklists, and any capacity gaps, such as the absence of manuals, lack of trained technicians, or missing tools, must be addressed before final approval.

Internal approval of donation plan

Following these assessments, the donation plan is consolidated and submitted to EMT leadership for internal approval. The plan outlines item descriptions, quantities, usability, and condition; summarizes the findings of the feasibility and needs assessments; identifies the proposed recipient; and describes any donor-specific compliance obligations. The plan must also document sustainability considerations, including how circularity principles, reverse logistics alternatives, and long-term impacts have been evaluated. Once reviewed and endorsed, all approvals are recorded and filed to support accountability, transparency, and audit readiness.

Agreement & formal documentation

Once approved, formal documentation is prepared. This involves preparing all required documentation to legally and operationally support the donation, including the Donation Certificate, Transfer of Ownership Form, Packing List, and GIK labels, all of which must clearly outline the terms of transfer. These documents specify non-commercial use restrictions, clarify liabilities and responsibilities, and detail expectations for maintenance, training, and safe use. Where applicable, cold chain logs are prepared, and all documents are translated into a language understood by the recipient. The donor and recipient jointly review and sign these materials before the handover to ensure clarity, consent, and shared understanding.

Packing, labelling, and handover preparation

Once the documentation is complete, the EMT prepares items for safe, compliant transfer. Items are packed securely using appropriate protective materials and labelled clearly with descriptions, quantities, expiry dates, batch numbers, and serial numbers. All boxes containing donated goods must be marked with “Donated – Not for Sale,” and reusable or repairable items should be highlighted using green labels, reflecting workshop best practices for promoting circularity. Temperature-sensitive commodities are stored and transported in accordance with cold chain requirements. The Logistics Lead ensures that physical items match the accompanying documentation and coordinates logistics and scheduling to ensure a smooth handover.

Physical transfer & sign-off

The handover occurs at an agreed-upon location and involves joint verification of items against inventory and documentation. Representatives of both the EMT and the recipient organization review and verify each item in person before signing the Donation Certificate and Transfer of Ownership Form. When appropriate, photographs are taken for verification, and if the donation includes medical equipment, brief on-site demonstrations or training may be provided. Responsibility for the items formally transfers to the recipient upon signature, and both parties retain signed copies of all documents.

Post-transfer monitoring & documentation

After the handover, the EMT conducts follow-up activities to ensure safe and effective use of the donated items. This includes confirming that equipment has been correctly installed, is fully functional, and is being used in accordance with recommended protocols. Follow-up also assesses whether maintenance, repair support, and training needs continue to be met, while monitoring circularity indicators such as reuse rates, repair rates, and environmentally safe disposal practices. Feedback from the recipient is gathered, and technical support may be provided remotely or in person if necessary. A Post-Handover Report is submitted to headquarters, and all documentation is archived to support transparency, institutional learning, and continuous improvement. Monitoring may continue for up to six months, depending on the nature, scale, and value of the donated items.

3.2. Donation process matrix

Table 2: The donation process matrix

Step	Description	Lead Role	Supporting Roles	Documents / Templates	Estimated Duration
i. Initiation	Identify surplus items, redundant stock, unused equipment, trigger review at end of mission, rotation, or upon formal request. Must consider reverse logistics before donation.	Logistics Lead	Team Leader, MTL, Pharmacist	Initiation Memo; Preliminary Inventory Summary	1-2 days

ii. Inventory & Categorization	Conduct full stock-take; classify items by usability, expiry, condition, and circularity indicators (repairability, refurbishment potential, hazard class).	Logistics Lead	Pharmacist, WASH/Biomedical Engineer	Stock Inventory Sheet; Waste & Circularity Classification Form	1-3 days
iii. Feasibility Assessment	Assess clinical relevance, safety, regulatory compliance, equipment compatibility, power requirements, local technical capacity, availability of spare parts, and environmental considerations.	Medical Team Lead	Pharmacist, WASH/Biomedical Engineer, Team Leader	Feasibility Note; Technical Compatibility Checklist	1-2 days
iv. Identify Recipient	Select potential recipients based on MoH/WHO coordination, system capacity, and ability to safely use, maintain, and dispose of items.	Team Leader	MoH, EMTCC, Logistics Lead	Recipient Profile, MoH/WHO Request or Confirmation	1 day
v. Needs Assessment	Conduct joint needs assessment; verify demand, infrastructure readiness, storage conditions, training needs, maintenance capacity, waste-handling capacity, and impact on local waste systems.	Team Leader	MTL, Logistics Lead, WASH/Biomedical Engineer	Needs Assessment Checklist, Technical Capacity Assessment	1-2 days
vi. Internal Approval	Review donation plan; check compliance with donor rules, national regulations, and environmental/circularity criteria.	Team Leader	Donor Focal Point, MTL, Pharmacist	Donation Plan; Approval Record	1 day

vii. Agreement & Documentation	Prepare formal donation documents; clarify ownership transfer, non-commercial use, liability, and technical responsibilities.	Logistics Lead	Team Leader, Recipient Representatives	Donation Certificate; Transfer of Ownership Form; GIK Labels; Packing List	1 day
viii. Packing & Prep	Pack items securely; label with expiry, batch, and “Donated – Not for Sale.” Identify green-labelled (reusable/repairable) items; maintain cold chain where needed.	Logistics Lead	Pharmacist, WASH/Biomedical Engineer	Packing List; Label Set; Cold Chain Log (if required)	1-2 days
ix. Physical Transfer	Conduct physical handover, verify inventory, obtain signatures, conduct on-site demonstration or operational training if applicable.	Logistics Lead	Recipient Organization, MTL, WASH/Biomedical Engineer	Signed Donation Certificate; Photo Record; Handover Acknowledgement	1 day
x. Post-Monitoring	Follow-up to confirm appropriate use; provide technical support if needed; collect circularity indicators (reuse rate, repair rate, safe disposal) and document lessons learned.	Team Leader	Logistics Lead, WASH/Biomedical Engineer, MoH	Post-Handover Report; Follow-up Checklist; Monitoring Log	14 days - 6 months

4. Additional guidelines

4.1. Pharmaceutical donations

Pharmaceuticals donated by or to EMTs must appear on the WHO Model List of Essential Medicines or national equivalents. They must have a remaining shelf life of at least 6 months, preferably 12 months. They must be labelled with INN, brand name, manufacturer, batch, and expiry. Items must be unopened, in original packaging, and stored under appropriate conditions. A Stock Donation Form and a Donation Certificate must accompany each donation. Controlled substances require additional layers of approval and documentation, including double verification and entry into a Controlled Drug Register. They must be handed over securely, ideally in the presence of regulatory representatives. In addition to standard quality checks, teams should avoid overstocking and prioritize donations that align with actual consumption

patterns. Behavioural change campaigns may be considered to reduce overuse of disposables (e.g., gloves) and promote rational use of pharmaceuticals.

4.2. Receiving donations

Incoming donations (Gifts in Kind) must be pre-approved through HQ or mission leads. They must undergo quality and need assessments using a GIK Assessment Tool and Donor Questionnaire. Donations must be accepted only if traceability, quality, and usage conditions are met. All incoming donations must include liability clauses and ownership documentation. Unsolicited donations are discouraged and may be declined if non-compliant. All incoming donations should be screened for relevance and sustainability. Items that are not compatible with local systems or that require complex maintenance should be declined. Donations should be accepted only if they do not impose disposal or repair obligations on the recipient.

4.3. Disposal of unsuitable items

Items unfit for donation must be disposed of ethically and safely. Criteria include expired or near-expiry products, damaged, opened, or used items, items failing cold chain or other storage requirements, and items rejected by regulatory or recipient authorities. Disposal methods include returning to original countries (reverse logistics), certified incineration, or licensed waste contractors. All disposals require a Disposal Act form with documentation of rationale, method, date, and witnesses. Disposal strategies should prioritize environmentally responsible methods, including compliant incineration and recycling where feasible. Teams should avoid leaving behind broken or unsuitable equipment and should coordinate with local authorities to ensure proper waste handling.

4.4. Documentation and records

The following documents must be completed and archived: Donation Plan, Stock Donation Form, Donation Certificate, Transfer of Ownership Form, Packing List and GIK Labels, Disposal Act (if applicable), Controlled Drug Register (if applicable), and Communication logs and consent letters. The retention period is a minimum of 5 years. Records must be auditable and shared with EMTCC, MoH, and donors as needed. Documentation should include a record of any training provided, spare parts handed over, and post-handover support plans. Waste volumes and equipment usage data should be monitored and reported to inform future deployments and improve sustainability.

5. References

Estonia Disaster Relief Team (EDRT) EMT Type 2. *SOP for Donation Management*

IFRC. (2022). Tool 20, Exit Strategy Guidance. In *Community engagement and accountability toolkit*. <https://www.ifrc.org/sites/default/files/2022-04/Tool-20.-Exit-strategy-guidance.docx>.

IMC. (2021). *Emergency Medical Teams Type 1 Manual*

Muñoz Beaulieu, I., Perez, R., Luneta, M., Eckenwiler, L., Hyppolite, S. R., Saeed, H. M., Schwartz, L., & Hunt, M. (2025). What remains after humanitarian organizations leave? An exploration of community perspectives regarding sustainability and humanitarian aid in the Philippines. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2025.105921>

Pal, N. E., Eckenwiler, L., Hyppolite, S.-R., Pringle, J., Chung, R., & Hunt, M. (2019). Ethical considerations for closing humanitarian projects: a scoping review. *Journal of International Humanitarian Action*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41018-019-0064-9>

Sitali, N., Briskin, E., Foday, J., Walker, C., Keus, K., Smart, F., Ali, E., & Whitehouse, K. (2022). What it takes to get it right: A qualitative study exploring optimal handover of health programmes in Tonkolili District, Sierra Leone. *Global Public Health*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/17441692.2022.2058047>

UK-Med EMT. *SOPs for Pharmaceutical Donation*

WHO Blue Book (2021). *Classification and Minimum Standards for Emergency Medical Teams*

Zhao, K., Xia, M. (2014). Forming Interoperability Through Interorganizational Systems Standards. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 30 (4), 269–298. <https://doi.org/10.2753/MIS0742-1222300410>

ANNEX 1

Donation checklist

#	Item	Yes / No / N/A	Comments / Details
1	A joint needs assessment has been conducted with the recipient organization.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
2	Items are classified under WHO EMT categories (pharmaceuticals, diagnostics, clinical equipment, etc.).	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
3	Donated items verified for quality, functionality, expiry, and contextual relevance.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
4	Pharmaceuticals and medical devices are WHO-prequalified, CE-marked, or meet national regulatory standards.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
5	Medical equipment is functional, safe, and accompanied by user manuals.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
6	Expiry dates for consumables/pharmaceuticals meet the minimum 6–12-month requirement.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
7	Cold chain or special storage requirements have been identified and are available.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
8	Required documentation prepared (Donation Certificate, Inventory & Packing List, Transfer of Ownership Form).	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
9	Internal approvals obtained (Team Leader, Pharmacist, Logistics Coordinator).	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
10	Items packed and labeled appropriately, including cold chain or logistics considerations.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
11	Compatibility with recipient infrastructure (power, space, interfaces) confirmed.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
12	Training needs for the recipient organization assessed and planned.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
13	Documentation is available in the recipient's working language.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
14	Waste management, disposal options, and environmental impact have been considered.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
15	GIK Assessment Tool and Donor Questionnaire fully completed.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	

16	Engagement with relevant stakeholders (MoH, EMTCC, WHO) conducted.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
17	Monitoring mechanisms and post-transfer responsibilities defined and agreed.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	

ANNEX 2

Donation certificate template

Date: _____

WHO EMT Classification of Donor: Type ____ EMT (Fixed / Mobile / Specialized)

Donor Organization: _____

Recipient Organization: _____

Transfer Location: _____

ID	Inventory No.	Item Description (Type, Manufacturer, Model, Serial No. Purchase Year)	Classification	Qty	Estimated Value	Expiry/Condition

Purpose of Donation: _____

All items are donated freely, not for sale, and intended for humanitarian health support in accordance with the WHO EMT minimum standards.

Prepared by: _____ Name: _____

Date: _____

Handover by (Donor):

Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Received by (Recipient):

Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Donor Representative:

Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

ANNEX 3

Transfer of ownership form

Donor _____ Organization: _____
 Recipient _____ Organization: _____
 Date of Transfer: _____
 WHO EMT Classification: Type ___ / Module: _____

Item Description	Serial/Batch	Quantity	Estimated Value	Expiry/ Condition	Donor Reference	Verified by (Clinical/ Biomed)

Ownership is officially transferred from the donor to the recipient in accordance with the WHO EMT minimum standards.

I confirm the above-listed items have been transferred and accepted.

Donor Representative:
 Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Recipient Representative:
 Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

ANNEX 4

GIK assessment tool

#	Question	Response Options	Comments / Details
1	Has the donation been formally solicited or requested by the recipient?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
2	Are the items classified appropriately (clinical, diagnostics, pharma, ICT, WASH, logistics)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Specify categories:
3	Are all items relevant, functional, and appropriate to the EMT scope of services?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
4	Item condition (select one):	<input type="checkbox"/> New <input type="checkbox"/> Used <input type="checkbox"/> Refurbished	If refurbished, compliant with WHO standards? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
5	Do items meet expiry standards (minimum 6–12 months remaining)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Expiry dates verified by:
6	Are donated medicines aligned with the national Essential Medicines List (EML) or WHO guidelines?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
7	Is the equipment compatible with recipient infrastructure (power, space, language)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Details:
8	Are cold chain or special storage/transport conditions required and feasible?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Cold chain required? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
9	Are manuals, labels, and user guides included and in appropriate language?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Missing items:
10	Has an environmental impact or disposal plan been identified and aligned with WHO/national guidelines?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Plan reference:
11	Are liability agreements and all required transfer documents complete?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Outstanding documents:
12	Is training or post-transfer technical support required?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	If Yes, responsible person/unit:
13	Is a monitoring and follow-up mechanism in place?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Monitoring method:

Reviewer:

Name: _____ Title: _____

Signature: _____ Date: _____

ANNEX 5

Disposal act template

Date: _____

Facility: _____

Item Description	Batch/ID	Quantity	Reason	Disposal Method	Witnesses

Reason: (1) Expired (2) Damaged (3) Recalled (4) Other: _____

Method (select): Incineration / Landfill / Reverse Logistics / Return to Donor/Other

Environmental Precautions Taken: _____

Prepared by:

Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Approved by:

Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Witness 1 (MoH/WHO):

Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Witness 2 (MoH/WHO):

Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

ANNEX 6

Controlled substances (DG) register template

Date	Substance	Batch No.	Qty Received (in)	Qty Dispensed (out)	Balance	Expiry	Verified By (Signature)

ANNEX 7

Inventory and packing list

Donor: _____

Recipient: _____

Transfer Date: _____

Module Type (WHO): Type 1 / 2 / 3 / Specialized / WASH / Other: _____

Box #	Item Description	Qty	Temp Req	Expiry/Condition	Remarks

Prepared and packed by:

Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Verified by:

Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

ANNEX 8

Donor questionnaire

Section	Question	Yes / No / N/A	Comments / Details
I. Coordination & Acceptance	Has the donation been coordinated and agreed upon with the recipient (MoH, WHO, EMTCC)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Have the items been specifically requested or formally accepted by the recipient?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Have the items been previously used or approved in the recipient country?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Are there donor-imposed conditions, restrictions, or obligations attached to the donation?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
II. Item Quality & Suitability	Are all items in good physical condition and within valid expiry dates?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Are items aligned with the national Essential Medicines List or WHO Model List?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Do the donated items meet local infrastructure and capacity requirements?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Are items WHO-prequalified or compliant with national/international regulatory standards?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Do any items include controlled substances or hazardous materials?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
III. Storage, Transport & Documentation	Have adequate storage and transport arrangements been ensured (including cold chain if required)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Are there special storage or handling requirements that must be met?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Are all items correctly labeled (batch no., expiry date, manufacturer)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Are all required documents available (packing list, donation certificate, customs forms, etc.)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
IV. Training, Support & Monitoring	Are user manuals, SOPs, or safety sheets included in the local language?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Is training on use, handling, storage, or maintenance planned or provided?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	

	Is post-transfer technical support or follow-up monitoring included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	
	Have feedback, data-sharing, and monitoring mechanisms been agreed with the recipient?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A	

Completed by:

Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

ANNEX 9

Damage & loss report template

Date of Report: _____

Reporting Officer: _____

Location: _____

Item	Batch/Serial No.	Qty affected	Nature of Loss/Damage	Estimated Value	Action Taken

Incident Summary: _____

Root Cause: Logistics / Storage / Handling / Other _____

Corrective Actions: _____

Prepared by:

Name: _____ Title: _____

Signature: _____ Date: _____

Verified by:

Name: _____ Title: _____

Signature: _____ Date: _____

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**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

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